

YOUTH IS THE BUILDER OF THE FUTURE

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Annotation: *This article discusses the opportunities created for young people and their important role in this regard. Achievements in the field of youth and education, as well as new opportunities in the new Uzbekistan are showing their place and effectiveness.*

Key words: *youth, society, education, youth policy, leadership, state awards, international community.*

INTRODUCTION We have all heard about young people for years. I admit that in recent years, the attention paid to young people by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has never been higher.

Implementation of youth policy, "Young Readers" Resolution No. 92 in MFYs, the formation of the staff of youth leaders, the formation of the youth balance, the introduction of state awards "Mard O'g'lon", "Kelajak Bunyodkori", the introduction of about 200 benefits, Allocation of quotas for admission, subsidized housing, additional quotas and funds for the "El-Yurt Umidi" Foundation for young people to study abroad, the slogan "Youth leisure, working hours of the leader" The organization of sports competitions, intellectual games, cultural and educational events in rural areas, the allocation of soft loans to young people who want to start a business, the resumption of the camp "Bostanliq" for young people repairs, for young people taking IELTS in English, state funding, "Future Leaders" clubs of talented, enterprising and leading young people have been established in the regions, along with training young people who want to study in various training courses and become self-employed.

MAIN PART

Fifty selected young people from "Future Leaders" clubs and aspiring youth, who successfully passed tests and oral question-and-answer exams, were sent to study at the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan as listeners of Future Leaders Season 2.

In this training course organized by the Agency for State Service Development under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, while studying at the SMA, we will be able to observe the process with our own eyes, along with the practical and theoretical knowledge of many experienced teachers. and provided us with the opportunity to practice in MFYs as well as in Ministries and agencies so that we could be a direct participant.

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Of course, studying at this school requires a lot of hard work, hard work and less sleep from the audience.

The lessons will be very interesting, we will not even know how the money was spent, and we will ask the teachers to share their knowledge and experience after the lesson, because there is little time and we need to use it effectively.

Another action was held in the framework of the national movement "Green Space". In a small area, teams from various fields, mostly young people, planted peacock trees. Uniting in good deeds and hashars is a value for our people. We also participated in the project with our promising young staff

studying at the SMA - listeners of the 2nd season of the "Leaders of the Future" program. It is good that in the coming years, this place will become a green park, and it is headed by young people, young civil servants, as well as the campaign continues throughout the country.

I think that the knowledge and skills we acquired while studying at the SMA could not be paid for much, and we were so lucky that education was absolutely free, while our salaries were saved, and dormitory expenses were also paid from the state budget. Personally, my opinion have changed 360 degrees in relation to the spheres, my love for my homeland and my country has increased. Kahramon Kuranbaev, First Deputy Adviser to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Cooperation with the State Service and Authorities, personally oversaw our activities at the university with the care and trust of our President.

The Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan encompasses: Atkham Sharipovich, Alisher Umarov, Mansur Bekmurodov, Otabek Khasanov, Sadullaev Alisher, Dilnozakhon Kattakhanova, Mansur Yunusov, Aktam Kholov and many others with many years of experience working without wasting time. The First Deputy Minister of Preschool Education Onorboev Bohodir Ochilboyevich did shared his knowledge and advice, taught leadership tactics and gave recommendations on working with documents, the heads of each department of the Ministry thank you for sharing and exchanging your experiences! All this is evidence of the fact that youth policy is being implemented in our country.

In the framework of the Protocol of Cooperation between the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the National Institute of Public Administration of the French Republic (INSP), Maria Charlotte, INSP Representative, is being presented on.

RESULTS

Listeners between the ages of 25 and 35 were selected from 1,862 candidates. and it gives me a strong sense of pride to be among them. The program is aimed at developing the competence of young staff, for 2 months students will learn in areas such as leadership, team building, time management, project management, strategic analysis, socio-economic development of the regions. The ministry is a backup to the heads of departments and is sent on foreign internships. Today, it is very important for the civil service to have personnel with the ability to identify and solve systemic problems, strategic thinking, analysis of opportunities.

I am proud to be a state servant, to serve the future of my country!

I would say to my peers, sisters, brothers, friends and all the young people of our country not to stop working on yourself. We are a force together. Let us unite as a nation and a people, using all our strength, energy, knowledge and experience, to include the Republic of Uzbekistan in the list of developed countries, to think about global problems, not small ones!

Let's not forget that this country, this Motherland is ours and its future depends on us! So that future generations will remember and be proud of us with good memories...

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